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SONNET – SOCIAL INNOVATION IN ENERGY TRANSITIONS

Co-creating a rich understanding of the diversity, processes, contributions, success and future potentials of social innovation in the energy sector

D5.3 (D22):

Report on econometric analysis of SONNET citizen survey, incl. cross-country comparison on individuals' perceptions and acceptance of SIE and EU energy transitions

Project Coordinator: Fraunhofer ISI (Karoline Rogge)

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Leader Organisation: GEM

Authors: Abigail Alexander-Haw, Elisabeth Dütschke, Valeria Fanghella, Marie-Charlotte Guetlein, Joachim Schleich

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Responsible scientist/administrator:	Marie-Charlotte Guetlein (GEM), Joachim Schleich (GEM), Elisabeth Dütschke (Fraunhofer ISI)
Contributor(s):	Abigail Alexander-Haw (Fraunhofer ISI), Valeria Fanghella (GEM)
Internal reviewer(s):	Heike Brugger (Fraunhofer ISI), Manuel Grieder (ZHAW), Karoline Rogge (ISI)

PROJECT PARTNERS

No	Participant name	Short Name	Country code	Partners' logos
1	Fraunhofer Society, with its Fraunhofer Institute of Systems and Innovation Research (Fraunhofer ISI)	ISI	DE	Fraunhofer ISI
2	Dutch Research Institute for Transitions	DRIFT	NL	
3	University of Sussex, with its Science Policy Research Unit (SPRU)	UoS	UK	
4	Grenoble Ecole de Management	GEM	FR	
5	Akademia Leona Kozminkiego	ALK	PL	
6	Zuercher Hochschule for Applied Research	ZHAW	CH	
7	ICLEI European Secretariat	ICLEI	DE	
8	City of Mannheim	MANN	GER	
9	City of Antwerp	ANTW	BE	
10	City of Bristol	BRIS	UK	
11	City of Grenoble	GREN	FR	
12	City of Warsaw	WARS	PL	
13	City of Basel (Associated Partner)	BASE	CH	

Executive Summary

SONNET aims to create an inter- and transdisciplinary understanding of the diversity and processes of social innovations in the energy sector (SIE) using an innovative mixed-method research design. As part of work package 5 of the SONNET project, the citizen survey gathers responses from approximately 6,000 participants in three countries: France, Germany, and Poland. The surveys consist of a general part and a specific part focussing on selected SIE.

This report presents and discusses the statistical-econometric results of the experiments on SIE carried out in the specific part of the survey. These experiments comprise of (i) a stated preferences discrete choice experiment which was conducted in France, Germany, and Poland on investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation; (ii) a stated preferences discrete choice experiment which was conducted in France on participation in renewable energy cooperatives; (iii) a stated preferences discrete choice experiment which was conducted in Germany on energy gamification through mobile applications; and (iv) an experiment with information treatment on campaigns against specific energy pathways which was implemented in Poland.

The results presented in this deliverable highlight the importance of financial attributes such as the rate of return, the risk associated with such investments, and low minimum investment requirements for investment projects into renewable energy (experiment (i)). They also emphasize a role for municipalities by matching the investments of citizens. In relation to country differences, we find that citizens in Poland appear more worried about the financial risks than citizens in France and Germany. As for experiment (ii) in France, it turns out that citizens prefer renewable energy cooperatives without the involvement of private companies, a one-member-one-vote rule and cooperatives that allow for high shares of self-consumption. In experiment (iii) on gamification through mobile apps in Germany, we find generally low interest in such an SIE, especially when subscription fees are high. With regard to the SIE on campaigns against certain energy pathways in Poland (experiment (iv)), we find that these campaigns tend to be perceived positively as indicated by the emotional response. Intentions to act, however, are less pronounced. Campaign arguments stressing the effects of an energy pathway on health and the environment appear more convincing than arguments stressing the effects on innovation and security of supply. In a next step, the outcomes from this deliverable will be used to assess the future potential of SIE in EU countries (deliverable D5.4).

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1 INTRODUCTION

Social innovations in the energy sector (SIE) have gained increasing interest from both academics and civil society actors by enabling sustainable energy transitions and also as a relevant field of experience and learning (Fressoli et al., 2014). SONNET aims to contribute to the comprehension of these processes by generating novel understandings of the diversity, processes and contributions of social innovation in the energy sector, and critically evaluating and assessing their success and future potential towards supporting sustainable transitions of energy systems.

WP5 aims to quantitatively examine citizen's individual perceptions of socio-economic, socio-cultural and socio-political enabling and impeding conditions of SIE and their acceptance to develop a better understanding of the potential scope and diffusion of SIE necessary for sustainable energy transitions. To this end, a demographically representative survey was implemented among ca. 6,000 participants in France, Germany, and Poland. The SONNET citizen survey consists of a general part and a specific part. The general part elicits information on household and individual characteristics of citizens (income, gender, environmental identity, etc.), acceptance of different types of SIE, and attitudes and behaviours regarding clean energy, energy technologies, policy mixes, etc. The key descriptive findings of the general part of the survey are reported in Deliverable D5.2.

The objective of this report is to present and discuss the statistical-econometric results of the experiments on SIE carried out in the specific part of the survey. These experiments comprise of (i) a stated preferences discrete choice experiment (DCE) which was carried out in France, Germany, and Poland on investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation; (ii) a DCE which was conducted in France on participation in renewable energy cooperatives; (iii) a DCE on energy gamification through mobile applications in Germany; and (iv) an experiment with information treatment consisting of three information treatments on campaigns against specific energy pathways which was implemented in Poland. The results shown in this report build on the research design as described in Deliverable D5.1 (on the final design of the citizen survey) and were analysed within task T5.5 employing state-of-the-art econometric methods. The findings of this Deliverable D5.3, combined with survey questions, will feed into the next deliverable of this WP, i.e. Deliverable 5.4 on the assessment of future potentials of SIE in European countries.

The remainder of this report is organized as follows. The next section describes the methodology employed including data collection, survey implementation and econometric models to analyse the DCEs. Section 3 then presents the design and the results of the DCE implemented in Germany, France and Poland on investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation. Similarly, Section 4 shows the design and results of the DCE carried out in France on participation in renewable energy cooperatives. Section 5 includes the DCE on energy gamification through mobile apps in Germany. Finally, Section 6 presents the design and the findings of the experiment conducted in Poland on campaigns against specific energy pathways and the results. Because the methodology to analyse this experiment differs from the econometric methodology presented in the next section it will also be described in Section 6. The deliverable closes with an outlook in Section 7.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection¹

The experiments were conducted as part of the SONNET citizen survey questionnaire which was implemented via the Qualtrics software. Prior to fielding the survey, extensive pre-tests were carried out with the English version and the responses obtained were used to test the length of the questionnaire and participants' understanding of the different tasks and questions. Some adjustments in wording and design of experiments were made before the final questionnaire was translated from English into national languages by professional translators. Translations were cross-checked by scientists from the project team for quality control. The actual survey was then administered in Germany, France and Poland through existing household panels of Norstat, a professional market research institute, via subcontracting. To allow for meaningful statistical results, a minimum sample size of approximately 2,000 observations per country was used. In each country, participants were selected via quota sampling using quotas for gender, age, region and income based on official EU or national statistics. In this sense, the surveys are demographically representative. To incentivize participation in the survey each participant who completed the survey received a small reward through Norstat's point system. Interviews were carried out in July and August 2021. The median response time across all three countries was about 20 minutes.

In order to ensure that quota requirements were met, participants answered screening questions on age (4-5 splits), gender, region (NUTS 2 or similar) and income (3 splits). Questions were formulated according to the quotas provided by GEM and based on official EU or national statistics. Participants who did not fulfil the quota requirements received a message informing them that they were not eligible to participate and were automatically directed back to the survey institute's website.

The survey contained two quality control questions. In both questions, participants were asked to check a particular option among all options available. Participants who failed to check the indicated option in both control questions were excluded from the survey and informed that their answers did not fulfil the quality standards.

Participants were considered to be speeders when the duration to complete the survey was less than 1/3 of the median time. Speeders were excluded from the analysis. The final number of participants considered in this deliverable was 2,096 in France (excluding 62 speeders), 1,997 in Germany (excluding 52 speeders), and 2,048 in Poland (excluding 54 speeders).

¹ The description of the data collection and the survey builds, largely verbatim, on D5.2.

2.2 Survey

Table 1 shows an outline of the survey.² The survey starts with an introduction informing participants about survey procedures, anonymity, privacy and data protection, as well as their right to withdraw at any time. The introduction is followed by the screening questions related to the age, gender, region, and income of participants to ensure that quota requirements are met and that only qualified participants take part. The screening questions are followed by the specific survey part on selected SIE types. The SIE types were identified in milestone MS7 based on SONNET's SIE typology (Π.2, D1.1) and the conceptual framework (Π.3, D1.2) developed in WP1. These are:

1. Investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation
(investigated in Germany, France and Poland)
2. Participation in renewable energy cooperatives
(investigated in France only)
3. Energy gamification through mobile apps
(investigated in Germany only)
4. Campaigns against specific energy pathways
(investigated in Poland only)

This specific part involves either one of three discrete choice experiments (DCEs) or – in Poland – one alternative experimental design. Thus, attitudes towards four different SIE types are investigated in depth. The subsequent general part of the survey includes questions related to citizens' willingness to participate in SIE, questions on attitudes towards policies and policy objectives, questions on general political orientation and trust in institutions, questions on individual behaviours (including environmental behaviours), attitudes, and preferences (including social preferences such as preferences for fairness or reciprocity). Key descriptive findings from the general part can be found in D5.2.

² D5.1 provides a more detailed description of the survey design.

Table 1: Survey outline

Part	Description	Participation
A	General Part: Introduction	Full sample
B	General Part: Screening questions	
C	Specific Part: Experiments	
C1	DCE on investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation	Half of sample in France, Poland and Germany
C2	DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives	Half of sample in France
C3	DCE on energy gamification through mobile apps.	Half of sample in Germany
C4	Experiment on campaigns against specific energy pathways using information treatments - treatment 1	Half of sample in Poland
C5	Experiment on specific energy pathways - treatment 2	Half of sample in Poland (from C1)
D	Specific Part: Survey Questions on Experiments	
D1	Questions on investment portfolio and decisions, items on financial literacy, loss and debt aversion	Participants in C1 and C2
D2	Questions on renewable energy cooperatives	Participants in C2
D3	Questions on mobile app usage and motivational factors	Participants in C3
D5	Questions related to experiment on campaigns against specific energy pathways	Participants in C4
E	General Part: Additional Survey Questions	
E1	Questions on participation in SIEs	Full sample
E2	Questions on policies and policy-making processes	
E3	Questions on political orientation and trust	
E4	Questions on financial and energy literacy, energy consumption and behaviours	
E5	Questions on personality and preferences	
E6	Questions on socio-demographics	

2.3 Econometric methodology for stated preferences discrete choice experiments (DCE)³

Participants in the three stated preferences discrete choice experiments (DCEs) on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation, participation in renewable energy cooperatives, and energy gamification through mobile apps are asked repeatedly to choose one option or alternative from a set of options or alternatives presented to them. For example, in the DCE implemented in France, Germany and Poland, participants are shown repeatedly two different renewable electricity generation projects and are asked to indicate in which of the two projects – if any – they would like to invest. A set of alternatives presented to participants is also called a choice set.

In all three DCEs, the alternatives in the choice sets differ on selected attributes including benefits / desirable features (e.g. rate of return, social comparison feedback) and costs / undesirable features (e.g. subscription fees, probability that the investment is lost). By choosing an alternative from a choice set participants make trade-offs between these attributes.

Each of our three DCEs consists of 24 choice sets with two choice alternatives each. To reduce cognitive burden, the choice sets are divided into three blocks of eight choice sets and participants in the DCE are randomly assigned to one block. Thus, each participant makes eight consecutive choices between two alternatives.

Importantly, the DCE methodology is consistent with random utility theory (RUT) (McFadden, 1974). As described by Louviere et al. (2010, p. 62), “RUT proposes that there is a latent construct called “utility” existing in a person’s head that cannot be observed by researchers. That is, a person has a “utility” for each choice alternative, but these utilities cannot be “seen” by researchers, which is why they are termed “latent”. RUT assumes that the latent utilities can be summarized by two components, a systematic (explainable) component and a random (unexplainable) component. Systematic components comprise attributes explaining differences in choice alternatives and covariates explaining differences in individuals’ choices. Random components comprise all unidentified factors that impact choices.”

Formally, in the DCEs N participants take part in a series of T choice sets. Each choice set includes j alternatives. The latent utility of a participant n choosing an alternative j in a choice set t can be written as:

$$U_{njt} = \beta_n X_{njt} + \varepsilon_{njt}, n = 1, \dots, N, \quad j = 1, 2, \quad t = 1, \dots, T \quad (1)$$

where X_{njt} is a vector of attributes (e.g. of an investment project in decentralized electricity generation), ε_{njt} reflects an error term, and β_n is a vector of random parameters.

³ The presentation of the mixed logit model is standard and follows, in parts verbatim, Faure et al. (2021).

We use mixed logit models to estimate the parameters associated with the attributes in the three DCEs. Mixed logit models allow preference parameters for particular attributes (e.g. costs or benefits) to vary across individuals (Revelt and Train, 1998). Unlike standard conditional logit models, mixed logit models therefore do not depend on the so-called Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA) assumption.

In particular, β_n is allowed to vary across participants and hence to capture heterogeneity in preferences for attributes across individuals. The vector β_n is characterized by a density function $f(\beta|\theta)$ with a vector of parameters θ (Train, 2003). Following the literature, we assume β_n to be normally distributed. As is standard in the literature, we assume that ε_{njt} is distributed iid extreme value. The probability to observe participant n choose a sequence of alternatives $s = (j_1, j_2, \dots, j_T)$ is then

$$S_n(\theta) = \int \prod_{t=1}^T \frac{\exp(\beta'_n X_{nit})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta'_n X_{njt})} f(\beta_n|\theta) d\beta_n \quad (2)$$

All parameters are estimated via maximum likelihood methods. The log likelihood function may be expressed as

$$LL(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^N \ln S_n(\theta) \quad (3)$$

Because no analytical solution exists for equation (2), the probability is approximated through simulations. More specifically, denoting the conditional probability that participant n chooses a sequence of alternatives for a known β_n by $P_n(\beta_n) = \prod_{t=1}^T \frac{\exp(\beta'_n X_{nit})}{\sum_{j=1}^J \exp(\beta'_n X_{njt})}$, we obtain the simulated log likelihood by running a simulation with R Halton draws (Train, 2003):

$$SLL(\theta) = \sum_{n=1}^N \ln \left\{ \frac{1}{R} \sum_{r=1}^R P_n(\beta_n^r) \right\} \quad (4)$$

where β_n^r is the r^{th} draw from $f(\beta_n|\theta)$. We used $R = 500$.

The marginal willingness to pay (WTP) for an attribute x may be estimated as:

$$\widehat{WTP}_x = -\frac{\hat{\beta}_x}{\hat{\beta}_p} \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{\beta}_x$ is the estimated random parameter associated with attribute x, and $\hat{\beta}_p$ is the estimated parameter associated with the cost attribute in the DCE.

3 DCE ON INVESTMENT PROJECTS IN DECENTRALIZED ELECTRICITY GENERATION (FRANCE, GERMANY, POLAND)

In this section, we present the discrete choice experiment (DCE) carried out in France, Germany, and Poland on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation. We are particularly interested in characteristics that might allow for a broader diffusion of such projects (e.g. renewable energy cooperatives) in the general population, and hence help increase the acceptance of the energy transition in these countries.

This section is organized as follows. First, we provide more details on the surveys and the sample. Then we describe the DCE design and report and discuss the results.

3.1 Survey

Excluding speeders and those who failed both attention checks, 2,096 participants in France, 1,997 participants in Germany, and 2,048 participants in Poland took part in our survey. In each country, approximately half the participants were randomly assigned to take part in the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation. Thus, 1,074 participants in France, 986 participants in Germany and 936 participants in Poland completed the DCE presented in this section.

Summary statistics for the three samples are displayed in Table 2. Table 2 also presents national population statistics for comparison. Due to varying income levels and different currencies⁴, different categories were used in the three countries. Overall, sample statistics are close to national statistics. In France, participants below the age of 30 and participants in the highest household income category are slightly underrepresented. In Germany, participants in the age category 30-49 years are slightly overrepresented. Finally, in Poland, participants in the lowest household income category are slightly underrepresented compared to the national average.

⁴ 1 PLN corresponded to 22 EUR cent in 2021, thus the three income classes for Poland are segregated by around 650EUR and 1290 EUR.

Table 2: Sample characteristics for participants in the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation

	France		Germany		Poland	
	Sample	Population	Sample	Population	Sample	Population
Share of males^a	49.9%	48.3%	49.0%	49.3%	48.1%	48.4%
Age (share of adult population)^b						
18-29	14.1%	17.6%	15.0%	16.5%	17.5%	17.4%
30-49	33.0%	32.3%	36.6%	30.3%	37.2%	36.9%
50-64	26.5%	24.5%	24.7%	27.3%	26.6%	24.1%
65 and older	26.4%	25.5%	23.6%	25.8%	18.6%	21.6%
Household income						
2,000 EUR or less ^c	38.6%	36%	-	-	-	-
2,001 – 4,000 EUR	40.7%	42%	-	-	-	-
More than 4,000 EUR	20.7%	23%	-	-	-	-
2,000 EUR or less ^d	-	-	31.6%	30%	-	-
2,001 – 3,600 EUR	-	-	28.3%	31%	-	-
More than 3,600 EUR	-	-	40.1%	39%	-	-
3,000 PLN or less ^e	-	-	-	-	24.7%	30%
3,001 – 5,900 PLN	-	-	-	-	41.5%	40%
More than 5,900 PLN	-	-	-	-	33.7%	30%

^a Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: Insee (2017). ^d Source of population statistics: Statistisches Bundesamt (2018). ^e Source of population statistics: ESS (2020).

3.2 DCE design

We used the following framing to introduce the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation:⁵

"In this part of the survey, we invite you to make a series of hypothetical choices between different investment options. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions.

*Imagine you are being offered the opportunity to **buy a share in a renewable power plant** of your choice such as a windfarm, a solar power plant, or a biogas plant **located in your municipality**. If you choose to invest, you would have to pay the capital requirement for the investment up front. You get to own part of the renewable energy plant. The other shareholders of the plant are other citizens and the municipality. The plant sells carbon-free electricity into the electricity grid and makes money over time. **As payments, you annually receive a portion of any profits the plant makes, and you are paid back your initial investment after 10 years.***

On the following pages, different investment options for a renewable power plant in your municipality will be offered to you. We would like to know which option you would choose, if

⁵ Instructions highlighted in 'bold' were also seen highlighted in 'bold' by participants.

these were your only options. Please make your choices as if you would likely make them in a real investment decision."

Participants were then asked to make a series of choice decisions between different investment projects which differed by the following attributes:

1. **Return on investment:** The amount of money you receive annually during the holding period as a share of your investment. For example, if the rate of return on capital is 10% and your investment is 1000 Euro, you receive 100 Euro per year. In addition, you receive your 1000 Euro at the end of the holding period (i.e. after 10 years). Return and initial investment will only be paid if the plant is not a total loss.
2. **Minimum investment requirement:** The smallest Euro amount that you need to invest to acquire a share in the renewable plant. Of course, you can invest more than the minimum investment requirement.
3. **Matching investment by municipality.** In some options, the municipality increases its investment in the plant in proportion to the amount of your investment.
4. **Risk of total loss.** There is a risk that your investment is permanently lost at any time during the holding period. For example, the economic conditions for the project may deteriorate, the project may be mismanaged, the technology may fail, the policy framework might change radically, or the project may get destroyed by an earthquake or a fire. Assume that there is no insurance to cover the financial losses associated with these events. For each option, the probability that this will happen is provided.
5. **Use of profits for nature conservation or support of low-income households:** 10% of the profits of the plant go to nature conservation measures in your municipality or are used to support low-income households in your municipality. Note that this has no impact on your return on investment. Remaining profits are reinvested in the plant.

The attributes and levels are shown in Table 3. In the survey for Poland, the monetary amounts used in the DCE were adjusted at the rate 1 EUR = 3 PLN to keep the relative value similar between countries in terms of purchasing power.

Table 3: Levels of different attributes considered in the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation

Attribute	Levels	Variable	Type
Return on investment	1%, 3%, 4%, 5%, 7%;	<i>rate</i>	continuous
Minimum investment requirement	100 EUR, 500 EUR, 1,000 EUR;	<i>min_low</i> <i>min_medium</i> (baseline)	dummy dummy
Matching investment by municipality	no matching, half the amount of your investment, the amount of your investment;	<i>no_match</i> <i>match_half</i> (baseline);	dummy dummy
Risk of total loss	1%, 3%, 5%;	<i>loss</i>	continuous
Use of profits	nature conservation measures in your municipality, support low-income households in your municipality;	<i>Nature</i> (baseline)	dummy

To limit the number of choice sets shown to participants and to increase the efficiency of the DCE design, we used a Bayesian-efficient design (Sándor and Wedel, 2001) using NGENE software (ChoiceMetrics, 2014). The priors used for the design were obtained from the pre-test. Our final design consisted of 24 choice sets with two alternatives each, divided into three blocks. Participants in the DCE were randomly assigned to one block and thus saw eight choice sets each. Figure 1 shows an example of a choice set used in the DCE.

Which of the two investments below would you choose?

Please, consider thoroughly how this investment will affect your budget, and that you actually are willing to pay the minimum investment requirement associated with the alternative that you choose.

(To read the explanations again, you can move the mouse over the text in the left column.)

	Investment A	Investment B
Return on investment	1%	3%
Minimum investment requirement	you have to invest at least 500€	you have to invest at least 1.000€
Matching investment by municipality	your municipality does not increase its investment	your municipality increases its investment by half the amount of your investment
Risk of total loss	1% chance of total loss	5% chance of total loss
Use of 10% of the profits of the plant	to support low-income households in your municipality	for nature conservation measures in your municipality

I choose: Investment A Investment B No investment

Figure 1: Example of a choice set in the DCE on investment projects in decentralized electricity generation

Our DCE design included two measures to mitigate the hypothetical bias inherent in DCEs. First, our framing included a so called 'cheap talk' script to produce more reliable estimates (Tonsor and Shupp, 2011). That is, participants were asked to make their choices as they would likely make them in a real investment decision. Second, our design included an opt-out option. That is, in addition to the two investment alternatives A and B shown in each choice task, participants could choose not to invest in either of the two alternatives.

To explore whether participants had understood key attributes of the DCE, the DCEs were followed by three comprehension questions with the response options a) true, b) false, and c) don't know.⁶ Participant who failed to provide correct responses had to re-read the instructions. Moreover, participants could read the explanations for each attribute again by moving their cursor over the attribute name in the choice sets.

Our choice of attributes and attribute levels was guided by the literature studying individuals' motives to join bottom-up sustainable energy initiatives (e.g. Sloot et al., 2019) and the literature employing DCE models in related contexts. In addition, we considered attributes which extant literature using DCE has not studied yet.

In the literature, financial benefits of investments in renewable energy cooperatives are measured either via changes in the electricity bill (e.g. Sagebiel et al., 2014; Knoefel et al., 2018; Azarova et al., 2019) or the rate of return (e.g. Vuichard et al., 2019; Pons-Seres de Brauwier and Cohen, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021). We followed the latter and used levels that are similar to those employed by Vuichard et al. (2019) and observed in cooperative investment projects in practice (e.g. IEA-RETD, 2016). Yet, they are substantially lower than in Cohen et al. (2021) who consider rates of return of up to 50%.

High minimum investment requirements have previously been identified as a barrier for low-income households to invest in renewable energy cooperatives and hence to participate in the energy transition (e.g. Lowitzsch, 2019).⁷ The attribute levels of 500 EUR and 1,000 EUR are similar to the reference investment levels in typical projects, while 100 EUR is below the minimum thresholds applied in practice (e.g. Cohen et al., 2021).⁸

The role of matching contributions by third parties has previously been explored in contexts such as charitable giving (e.g. Eckel and Grossman, 2003; Karlan and List, 2007; Meier, 2007) and the willingness to offset travel-related CO₂-emissions (e.g. Kesternich et al., 2016; Schwirplies et al., 2019). To our knowledge, previous studies on investments in energy cooperatives have not

⁶ The three manipulation check statements were: 1) If the minimum investment amount is 500€, this means that you cannot invest less than 500€ (correct answer: true); 2) If the minimum investment amount is 500€, this means that you cannot invest more than 500€ (correct answer: false); 3) If the municipality matches your investment, this has no effect on your rate of return, i.e. the amount of money you receive annually during the holding period (correct answer: true). Shares of correct responses for question 1) were 81% in France, 84% in Germany, and 81% in Poland. Shares of correct responses for question 2) were 83% in France, 87% in Germany, and 81% in Poland. Shares of correct responses for question 3) were 43% in France, 52% in Germany, and 43% in Poland.

⁷ See, in particular, the H2020 project SCORE (Supporting Consumer Ownership in Renewable Energies) (www.score-h2020.eu) which aims to facilitate co-ownership of renewable energies for consumers.

⁸ In a choice experiment on energy cooperatives conducted in the frame of the H2020 project SocialRES, Wu et al. (2021) also use minimum investment amount as an attribute with six levels ranging between 50 EUR and 5,000 EUR.

considered matching. We limited the matching to 100% because findings by Karlan and List (2007) suggest that higher rates (of 200% and 300%) have no additional effect.

Previous research on participation in energy cooperatives suggests that project risk may affect investments in these projects (e.g. Salm et al., 2016). Since low-income households tend to be more risk averse than high-income households (e.g. Meissner et al., 2020), project risk may be a barrier in particular for low-income households to investments in decentralized electricity generation projects. Previous DCE analyses of energy cooperatives did not explicitly consider this aspect. Therefore, we included the risk that the investment is permanently lost at any time during the holding period as an attribute in the DCE. It proved difficult to obtain empirical data on total losses of such projects. According to Branner and Ghadirian (2014), annual failure rates for blades due to excessive loading or fatigue damage range between 0.06% and 0.29%. Hence, the figures chosen in our DCE seem generally plausible, even though the high end of the range may be above the rates of total losses observed in practice.

Our final attribute captures co-benefits of projects in decentralized electricity generation for the municipality where the project is located. Ek and Persson (2014) include as an attribute whether a share of the project revenue is transferred to the local community and earmarked for nature conservation measures or not. In our DCE we distinguished whether a share of the profits is used for nature conservation measures or to support low-income households in the participants' municipality. Supporting low-income households may help mitigate the effects of increasing energy costs in the wake of the energy transition. For example, carbon taxes are typically regressive unless the revenues are redistributed (e.g. Feindt et al., 2021).

Finally, we note that unlike the thrust of the existing literature (e.g. Ek and Persson, 2014; Lienhoop, 2018; Azarova et al., 2019; Vuichard et al., 2019; Cohen et al., 2021), our DCE is technology-neutral. Similar to Knoefel et al. (2018) and Sagebiel et al. (2014), we decided not to include technology type such as wind turbines or solar photovoltaic plants neither in the framing to avoid confounding or distraction, nor as an attribute because the empirical literature on technology acceptance suggests that people prefer solar plants to other renewable technologies such as wind mills or biomass (e.g. Kaenzig et al., 2013). This decision was confirmed by findings presented in D5.2 (see Figure 10, p. 12) which corroborate the general preference for renewable energy sources with some difference between the countries regarding the specific energy source (e.g. weaker preferences for wind in France compared to Poland and Germany).

3.3 Results

To explore individual preferences for investment projects in decentralized electricity generation we estimate two types of models: a pooled model and single country models. In the pooled model we stack observations from the samples in France, Germany, and Poland and include interaction terms between country-specific dummy variables and the attributes using Germany as the base country. That is, we estimate the following specification of the mixed logit model given in equation (1):

$$\begin{aligned}
U_{njt} = & \text{status_quo} (\beta_{1n} + \beta_2 * FR + \beta_3 * PL) + \text{rate} (\beta_{4n} + \beta_5 * FR + \beta_6 * PL) + \\
& \text{loss} (\beta_{7n} + \beta_8 * FR + \beta_9 * PL) + \text{min_low} (\beta_{10n} + \beta_{11} * FR + \beta_{12} * PL) + \\
& \text{min_medium} (\beta_{13n} + \beta_{14} * FR + \beta_{15} * PL) + \text{no_match} (\beta_{16n} + \beta_{17} * FR + \beta_{18} * PL) + \\
& \text{match_half} (\beta_{19n} + \beta_{20} * FR + \beta_{21} * PL) + \text{nature} (\beta_{22n} + \beta_{23} * FR + \beta_{24} * PL) + \varepsilon_{njt},
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

The variable *status_quo* is a dummy variable that takes on the value one for the opt-out option and zero for all other choice alternatives. The variables *rate*, *loss*, *min_low*, *min_medium*, *no_match*, *match_half*, and *nature* refer to the DCE attributes and levels as described in Table 3. *FR* and *PL* are dummy variables that take on the value one for participants from France and Poland, respectively, and zero otherwise. Therefore, the results for Germany appear in the column labelled 'Baseline' in Table 4. Columns labelled 'Interaction with FR' and 'Interaction with PL' show coefficients of the interaction terms with *FR* and *PL*, respectively. If these coefficients turn out to be significant, this implies that the findings for the relevant country are significantly different from the findings in Germany.

In the single country models, we use the samples in one country only, without interaction terms. The pooled model allows us to test for differences in the coefficients across countries, i.e. for differences in preferences for attributes. However, the pooled model assumes the error term to be identical across countries. In addition, the country dummies are a 'catch-all' for various kinds of country-specific effects including culture, institutions, economic, and social conditions. In comparison, the single-country models allow for different error terms across countries, but do not allow us to test for differences in coefficients across countries. We present the findings for the country-specific models in Table 6.

First, we refer to the lower part of Table 4, which reports the standard deviations of the parameter estimates. All but one standard deviation are statistically significant, suggesting heterogeneity in attribute preferences across participants and corroborating the use of a mixed logit model. The upper part of Table 4 which shows the mean estimate of the coefficients of the (latent) utility function in equation (6), suggests that all coefficients are statistically significant.

We first note that the coefficient associated with the *status_quo* variable is negative for all three countries. Because the *status_quo* variable captures participants' choice of the opt-out option the negative coefficients imply that on average participants prefer one of the two hypothetical investment projects in decentralized electricity generation shown to them in the DCE.

Table 4: Results of pooled mixed logit models for DCE on investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation

Baseline		Interaction with <i>FR</i>		Interaction with <i>PL</i>	
Mean					
<i>status_quo</i>	-1.8427*** (0.216)	<i>status_quo_fr</i>	-0.4854* (0.283)	<i>status_quo_pl</i>	-0.4365 (0.291)
<i>rate</i>	0.4240*** (0.029)	<i>rate_fr</i>	-0.0500 (0.040)	<i>rate_pl</i>	-0.1991*** (0.041)
<i>loss</i>	-0.5787*** (0.028)	<i>loss_fr</i>	-0.0251 (0.038)	<i>loss_pl</i>	0.1394*** (0.039)
<i>min_low</i>	0.6404*** (0.080)	<i>min_low_fr</i>	0.0489 (0.110)	<i>min_low_pl</i>	-0.3492*** (0.113)
<i>min_medium</i>	0.4483*** (0.066)	<i>min_medium_fr</i>	0.0924 (0.091)	<i>min_medium_pl</i>	-0.2208** (0.094)
<i>no_match</i>	-0.9631*** (0.083)	<i>no_match_fr</i>	0.3339*** (0.113)	<i>no_match_pl</i>	0.5525*** (0.116)
<i>match_half</i>	-0.3839*** (0.061)	<i>match_half_fr</i>	0.2334*** (0.084)	<i>match_half_pl</i>	0.2877*** (0.087)
<i>nature</i>	0.4180*** (0.066)	<i>nature_fr</i>	0.1665* (0.092)	<i>nature_pl</i>	-0.0564 (0.094)
Standard deviation					
<i>status_quo</i>	4.3798*** (0.136)				
<i>rate</i>	0.3226*** (0.017)				
<i>loss</i>	0.4141*** (0.015)				
<i>min_low</i>	1.3343*** (0.051)				
<i>min_medium</i>	0.3856*** (0.088)				
<i>no_match</i>	0.6317*** (0.060)				
<i>match_half</i>	0.0143 (0.074)				
<i>nature</i>	1.2293*** (0.045)				
Log likelihood	-18,582.134				
Participants	2,996				
Observations	71,904				

Standard errors in parentheses; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

As expected and consistent with previous literature (e.g. Vuichard et al., 2019; Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021), participants in all three countries prefer projects with higher rates of return. We find no difference in these preferences between France and the

base country Germany at $p < 0.1$. In comparison, the average participant from Poland appears to care less about the rate of return than the average participant from Germany.⁹

In all three countries and similar to Cohen et al. (2021), participants dislike higher chances of losing their entire investment. While these preferences do not appear to differ between France and Germany, the coefficient for the sample from Poland appears to be lower than for the sample from Germany. For a more substantive interpretation of our findings, we calculate the estimated marginal willingness to pay using equation (5). In this case, willingness to pay is measured as a percentage point change in the rate of return (see Table 5). Accordingly, the average participant from Germany and France is willing to give up about 1.4 percentage points of return for a 1 percentage point decrease in the risk to experience a total loss. At about 1.9 percentage points, this figure is even higher for Poland. These findings are supported by results from a standard 5-point Likert scale on risk-aversion which asks participants how willing they are to take risks. On average, participants from Poland are more risk averse than participants from France and Germany ($p < 0.01$), while we find no difference between France and Germany.

Next, the findings for *min_low* and *min_medium* imply that participants in all three countries prefer a minimum investment requirement of 100 EUR and 500 EUR instead of the baseline level of 1,000 EUR. Moreover, a Wald test shows that the coefficient for *min_low* is significantly larger than the coefficient for *min_medium* ($p < 0.05$). While there appears to be no difference in the coefficients associated with *min_low* and *min_medium* between France and Germany, the coefficient in Poland is statistically significantly lower than in these countries. In terms of willingness to pay, participants in all three countries are willing to give up about 1 percentage point of return for a minimum investment requirement of 500 EUR instead of 1,000 EUR (see Table 5). If the minimum investment requirement was 100 EUR instead of 1,000 EUR, participants from France and Germany would be willing to give up about 1.5 percentage points in return, and participants from Poland would be willing to give up about 1.3 percentage points. Hence, participants in all three countries appear to enjoy lower minimum investment requirements at a decreasing rate, and differences across countries appear to be modest.

In all three country samples, participants prefer, as expected, a full matching of their investment by the municipality over a 50% matching or no matching. A Wald test for equality of the coefficients for *no_match* and *half_match* further shows that a 50% matching is preferred to no matching ($p < 0.01$). This finding is in line with the empirical literature on the role of matching in other contexts (e.g. Eckel and Grossman, 2003; Karlan and List, 2007; Meier, 2007; Kesternich et al., 2016; Schwirplies et al., 2019). For both matching levels, preferences are less pronounced in France and in Poland than in Germany. As can be seen from Table 5, participants from Germany, France, and Poland would be willing to give up about 2.3, 1.7, and 1.8 percentage points in return if their investment in the project was fully matched rather than not matched. In comparison, participants from all three countries would be willing to pass on about 1.4 percentage points in return if the municipality matched half of their investment rather than not matching their

⁹ The coefficient associated with rate for Poland is calculated as $0.4240 - 0.1991 = 0.2249$.

investment at all.¹⁰ These findings imply that participants in all three countries value matching at decreasing rates as matching increases.

Finally, we find that participants in all three countries prefer that profits be used for nature conservation measures in participants' municipality rather than for the support of low-income households in their municipality. This result is consistent with Ek and Persson (2014) in a similar context. This finding may be explained by self-interest because on average participants may expect to benefit directly from the amenities of local environmental protection measures. In contrast, only low-income households would benefit from dedicating the profits to fund low-income households. While we observe no differences in these preferences between Germany and Poland, the sample from France has statistically significantly stronger preferences for nature conservation measures (compared to supporting low-income households) than the samples from Germany and Poland. Participants from Germany and Poland are willing to give up about 1 percentage point in returns if profits are used to fund nature conservation measures rather than low-income households in their municipality (see Table 5).

Table 5: Estimated willingness-to-pay for attributes of investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation (measured as a percentage point change in the rate of return)

	Germany	France	Poland
<i>loss</i>	-1.365	-1.365	-1.953
<i>min_low</i>	1.510	1.510	1.295
<i>min_medium</i>	1.057	1.057	1.012
<i>no_match</i>	-2.271	-1.682	-1.826
<i>match_half</i>	-0.905	-0.402	-0.428
<i>nature</i>	0.986	1.563	0.986

The results of the single-country models are reported in Table 6. Overall, they are very similar to the findings of the pooled model shown in Table 4. The only noticeable difference pertains to the coefficient associated with *match_half* in Poland which turns out to not be statistically significant in the single-country model for Poland. The difference to the finding in the pooled model is possibly due to the lower power in the single-country model. Estimates of the willingness to pay, which are not shown to save space, are also very similar to those reported in Table 5, except for Poland, where the willingness-to-pay estimate for *match_half* is zero and for *nature* about 50% higher (i.e. about 1.5 rather than about 1) in the single-country mode than in the pooled model.

¹⁰ To calculate this figure, we used the difference between the willingness-to-pay estimates for *no_match* and *match_half* in Table 5.

Table 6: Results of single-country mixed logit models for DCEs on investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation

	Germany	France	Poland
Mean			
<i>status_quo</i>	-1.8070*** (0.193)	-2.3988*** (0.185)	-2.5443*** (0.237)
<i>rate</i>	0.4394*** (0.032)	0.3779*** (0.029)	0.2205*** (0.028)
<i>loss</i>	-0.6122*** (0.032)	-0.6097*** (0.031)	-0.4032*** (0.028)
<i>min_low</i>	0.6540*** (0.079)	0.6845*** (0.079)	0.2201*** (0.085)
<i>min_medium</i>	0.4807*** (0.068)	0.5450*** (0.065)	0.1975*** (0.070)
<i>no_match</i>	-1.0218*** (0.090)	-0.6228*** (0.083)	-0.3467*** (0.083)
<i>match_half</i>	-0.4147*** (0.062)	-0.1577*** (0.060)	-0.0691 (0.064)
<i>nature</i>	0.4684*** (0.073)	0.5906*** (0.063)	0.3417*** (0.068)
Standard deviation			
<i>status_quo</i>	4.1664*** (0.219)	4.4509*** (0.213)	4.4698*** (0.232)
<i>rate</i>	0.4143*** (0.032)	0.3253*** (0.026)	-0.1881*** (0.038)
<i>loss</i>	0.4678*** (0.028)	0.4353*** (0.025)	0.3508*** (0.026)
<i>min_low</i>	-1.1031*** (0.090)	1.4404*** (0.086)	1.5596*** (0.094)
<i>min_medium</i>	-0.0533 (0.313)	0.3642*** (0.140)	-0.7536*** (0.106)
<i>no_match</i>	0.8365*** (0.092)	-0.6780*** (0.098)	-0.4572*** (0.116)
<i>match_half</i>	-0.1095 (0.142)	-0.0687 (0.129)	-0.0085 (0.124)
<i>nature</i>	-1.4275*** (0.084)	1.1251*** (0.072)	-1.2657*** (0.080)
Log likelihood	-6,153.425	-6,586.183	-5,782.230
Participants	986	1,074	936
Observations	23,664	25,776	22,464

Standard errors in parentheses; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

3.4 Conclusions

Our findings regarding the DCEs on investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation in Germany, France, and Poland generally suggest that in all three countries, participants on average prefer projects with a higher rate of return, a lower risk of total loss and a lower minimum investment requirement. Likewise, they value matching of their investment by their municipality, and using profits to fund environmental protection measures rather than low-income households in their municipality. We also find differences in participant valuation of project attributes across countries. For example, in terms of willingness to pay, participants from Poland appear to be more responsive to total project loss than participants from Germany and France. In comparison, participants from Germany appear to react more strongly to a matching

of their investment than participants from France and especially Poland. We further find that participants from France more strongly prefer to use a share of the project profits to finance local environmental protection measures instead of low-income households than participants from Germany and Poland. Finally, we find no noticeable difference in participant willingness to pay for a minimum investment requirement across countries. These findings provide valuable insights for the design of business models of projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation, which will be discussed in detail in Deliverable D5.4.

4 DCE ON PARTICIPATION IN RENEWABLE ENERGY COOPERATIVES (FRANCE)

In this section, we present the discrete choice experiment (DCE) carried out in France on participation in renewable energy cooperatives (REC). We are particularly interested in participant valuation of characteristics that would facilitate commercial investors' engagement in such projects and thus providing capital necessary to finance the energy transition in France.

We organize this section as follows. First, we provide more details on the surveys and the sample. Then we describe the DCE design and report and discuss the results.

4.1 Survey

In France, 1,022 participants completed the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives. Summary statistics for the sample are presented in Table 7 next to national population statistics for comparison. Overall, sample statistics are close to national statistics, though participants below the age of 30 are slightly underrepresented.

Table 7: Sample characteristics for participants in the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

	Sample	Population
Share of males^a	49.8%	48.3%
Age (share of adult population)^b		
18-29	13.9%	17.6%
30-49	33.3%	32.3%
50-64	25.8%	24.5%
65 and older	27.0%	25.5%
Household income		
2,000 EUR or less ^c	37.1%	36%
2,001 – 4,000 EUR	40.4%	42%
More than 4,000 EUR	22.4%	23%

^a Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: Insee (2017).

4.2 DCE design

To introduce the DCE on investments in RECs, we used the following framing:¹¹

¹¹ Instructions highlighted in 'bold' were also seen highlighted in 'bold' by participants.

"In this part of the survey, we invite you to make a series of hypothetical choices between different investment opportunities in renewable energy cooperatives. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions.

Renewable energy cooperatives (RECs) are organizations that own or operate renewable energy plants such as solar power plants, wind farms or biogas plants. They are controlled by their members or shareholders who finance investments in the renewable energy projects. Members are other private citizens and, in some cases, also municipalities and local private enterprises.

*Imagine you are being offered the opportunity to **become a member and invest in a renewable energy cooperative (REC) in your municipality**. The REC sells carbon-free electricity into the electricity grid and makes money over time. If you invest in the REC, you annually receive a portion of any profits the REC makes. Your membership ends after 10 years and you are paid back your initial investment. The smallest Euro amount that you need to invest to acquire a share in the renewable plant is 100 Euro. Of course, you can invest more. As a member, you will also gain voting rights to participate in the decision-making of the REC (e.g. to decide in which activities funds should be invested). On the following pages, different RECs will be presented to you. We would like to know in which REC you would invest if these were your only options. You may assume that all RECs are located within your municipality and produce electricity using your preferred technology (e.g. using solar plants, wind farms, biogas, ...). Please make your choices as if you would likely make them in a real investment decision.*

Participants were then asked to make a series of choice decisions between different investment projects which differed by the following attributes:

- 1. Type of members:** Some RECs allow only citizens to become members and invest. Other RECs also allow the local municipality or local private enterprises to become members.
- 2. Voting rights:** In some RECs, each member has one vote and can participate equally in the REC's governance. In other RECs, the voting rights are based on the capital contribution. This means that members who invest more have more influence on the REC's governance compared to members who invest less. However, citizens and the local municipality always hold more voting rights than private enterprises, no matter how much private enterprises invest.
- 3. Delegation of voting rights to a proxy:** In some RECs presented to you, citizens do not have to participate in the REC's governance themselves but can delegate their voting rights to a proxy who will then represent them. In other RECs, citizens must participate in the REC's governance themselves and cannot delegate their voting rights.
- 4. Return on investment:** The amount of money you receive annually during the holding period as a share of your investment. For example, if the rate of return on capital is 10% and your investment is 1000 Euro, you receive 100 Euro per year. In addition, you receive your 1000 Euro at the end of the holding period (i.e. after 10 years). Return and initial investment will only be paid if the plant is not a total loss.
- 5. Self-consumption:** Some RECs sell electricity directly to their members. If you become a member and invest in one of the RECs presented to you, you can purchase 0%, 35%, or 70% of

the electricity your household uses directly from this REC. The electricity cost to your household remains unchanged (i.e. electricity cost is the same as under your current electricity contract).

The attributes and levels are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Levels of different attributes considered in the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

Attribute	Levels	Variable	Type
Type of members	Citizens only, citizens and municipality, citizens, municipality and local private enterprises;	(baseline) <i>municip</i> <i>firms</i>	dummy dummy
Voting rights	one member one vote, based on capital;	(baseline) <i>cap_cont</i>	dummy
Delegation of voting rights to a proxy	possible, not possible;	<i>delegate</i> (baseline)	dummy
Return on investment	1%, 3%, 4%, 5%, 7%;	<i>rate</i>	continuous
Self-consumption	0%, 35%, 70%;	(baseline) <i>self35</i> <i>self70</i>	dummy dummy

As in the previously described DCE, we employed a Bayesian-efficient design (Sándor and Wedel, 2001) using the NGENE software (ChoiceMetrics, 2014) and relying on priors obtained from a pre-test with 50 participants. Our final design consisted of 24 choice sets with two alternatives each, divided into three blocks. Participants in the DCE were randomly assigned to one block and thus saw eight choice sets each. Figure 2 shows an example of a choice set used in the DCE.

To mitigate hypothetical bias and as described in the previous DCE, we included 'cheap talk' and an opt-out option (see Figure 2). We also included three comprehension questions with response options : a) true, b) false, and c) don't know.¹² Participant who failed to provide correct responses had to re-read the instructions. Moreover, participants could read the explanations for each attribute again by moving their cursor over the attribute name in the choice sets.

¹² The three manipulation check statements were: 1) If voting rights are based on capital contribution, members who invest more have more influence on the REC's governance compared to members who invest less (correct answer: true); 2) Private enterprises can hold more voting rights than citizens and the local municipality (correct answer: false); 3) Purchasing electricity from the REC has no impact on your household's electricity costs (correct answer: true). The shares of correct responses were 50%, 41% and 37% for questions 1, 2 and 3, respectively, highlighting the importance of the manipulation check and the necessity for participants to reread the instructions.

In which of the following renewable energy cooperatives would you like to invest?

Please consider thoroughly how this investment will affect your budget, and that you actually are willing to invest at least 100€ in the alternative that you choose.

	Cooperative A	Cooperative B
Type of members	citizens only	citizens and municipality
Voting rights	based on capital contribution	one member one vote
Delegation of voting rights to a proxy	possible	not possible
Return on investment	7%	3%
Self-consumption	35%	70%

	Cooperative A	Cooperative B	None of these cooperatives
I would like to become a member and invest 100€ or more in:	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

Figure 2: Example of a choice set in the DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

Our choice of attributes and attribute levels was guided by the literature studying individual motives to join bottom-up sustainable energy initiatives (e.g. Sloot et al., 2019) and the literature employing DCE models in related contexts. In particular, the attributes are assumed to reflect the challenges and potential trade-offs for RECs to include municipalities and/or commercial investors to accelerate the diffusion and scale of RECs while retaining the incentives and benefits of individual consumer participation. Finally, the attributes reflect criteria which RECs must satisfy according to the recast of the Renewable Energy Directive 2018/2001 (RED II) to benefit from an 'enabling framework' for RECs specified by individual Member States. Pursuant to Article 2 (16) of Directive 2018/2001 these criteria pertain to eligibility (shareholders or members are natural persons, small and medium sized enterprises (SMEs) or local authorities, including municipalities), ownership and control (must effectively be controlled by shareholders or members that are located in the proximity of the project, i.e. 51% of shares must be owned by these actors; must be autonomous, i.e. no individual shareholder must own more than 33% of the stock), the primary purpose (must provide environmental, economic or social community benefits for its shareholders or members or for the local areas where it operates, rather than financial profits), and membership (non-discriminatory voluntary participation open to all potential local members) (see also Hoicka et al., 2021).

Against this background, the attribute 'type of membership' reflects the provisions of RED II and distinguishes between three types of membership structures. That is, shares of the REC may be owned by citizens only (baseline), by citizens and the municipality, or by citizens, the municipality and local private enterprises. Previous research in related contexts suggests that citizens may dislike involvement of commercial investors in decision-making (Ek and Persson, 2014; Brennan and Rensburg, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021).

There are various governance models which enable citizens' participation in renewables projects. The cooperative governance model has been the most popular legal structure for small-scale RECs in Europe in the past (e.g. Caramizaru and Uihlein, 2020). This model entails the 'one-member, one vote' principle regardless of the share of stock owned by a member. This principle may scare off (local) commercial investors because their representation in supervisory bodies and their impact on management decisions would not adequately reflect their financial involvement (e.g. Hoicka et al., 2021). Therefore, in our DCE we also allowed voting rights to be proportional to the shareholding, similar to Sagebiel et al. (2014). In this case, to be in line with RED II regulation, citizens and the local municipality were assumed to hold the majority of voting rights.

Under the cooperative governance model, the general assembly is the highest decision making body. A certain number of voting rights must be represented at the general assembly in order for the body to have a quorum. The possibility to participate at these meetings and to be actively involved in the governance of RECs may be important for citizen shareholders to join a REC (see SONNET Deliverable D3.2). At the same time, preparing and participating at these meetings involves transaction costs. We therefore also included the possibility to delegate voting rights to a proxy as an attribute.

Owning shares in RECs leads to financial benefits. Following Vuichard et al. (2019), Pons-Seres de Brauwier and Cohen (2020), and Cohen et al. (2021), we assumed that shareholders receive an annual return on their investment. The levels used in our DCE are similar to those used by Vuichard et al. (2019) and observed in cooperative investment projects in practice (e.g. IEA-RETD, 2016).

The EU Clean Energy Package legal framework of regulation (EU) 2018/1999 allows RECs to share electricity between members and shareholders, even when this involves using the public grid. Our final attribute captures this option, varying the share of their electricity consumption participants may purchase directly from the REC. A recent survey of the adult population in France suggests that 68% of the respondents would be interested in producing and using their own energy (from PV), even if it was a bit more expensive, 31% of the respondents would like to produce enough electricity to be autonomous. Similarly, 51% of the respondents stated that becoming energy autonomous would be a reason to generate electricity at home. Only energy cost savings appeared to be more important than energy autonomy (ADEME and Opinion Way, 2019).

Because we are primarily interested in the socio-psychological aspects of self-consumption and to avoid confounding of this attribute with the attribute reflecting financial benefits (i.e. rate of return), we assumed that the electricity cost to the household does not vary with the share of electricity self-consumed. Indeed, for many prosumers self-consumption appears to be driven by non-financial motives such as the motive for autonomy mentioned earlier. Similarly, Gautier et al. (2019) find that about 40% of owners of residential PV modules self-consume electricity when there are no financial incentives to do so. In particular, they find that prosumers with high environmental motives are more prone to adapt their electricity consumption to help synchronize household electricity consumption and production.

Finally, we want to point out that the DCE on participation in RECs is technology-neutral, as the DCE on investment projects in renewable electricity generation described in section 3.

4.3 Results

We estimate the following specification of the mixed logit model:

$$U_{njt} = \beta_{1n}status_quo + \beta_{2n}rate + \beta_{3n}municip + \beta_{4n}firms + \beta_{5n}cap_cont + \beta_{6n}delegate + \beta_{7n}self35 + \beta_{8n}self70 + \varepsilon_{njt}, \quad (7)$$

The variable *status_quo* is a dummy variable that takes on the value one for the opt-out option and zero for all other choice alternatives. The variables *rate*, *loss*, *min_low*, *min_medium*, *no_match*, *match_half*, and *nature* refer to the DCE attributes and levels as described in Table 8.

The results of estimating the mixed logit model on RECs in France appear in Table 9. Looking first at the lower part of Table 9 which displays the standard deviations of the parameter estimates we note that six of the eight estimates of the standard deviations are statistically significant. This finding suggests heterogeneity in attribute preferences across participants and corroborates our use of a mixed logit model to analyse the data obtained from the DCE. The upper part of Table 9 reports the mean estimate of the coefficients of the (latent) utility function in equation (7). Accordingly, all coefficients associated with the attributes in the DCE, except the coefficient for *municip*, are statistically significant.

The negative coefficient associated with the *status_quo* which captures participants' choice of the opt-out option suggests that on average participants prefer one of the two hypothetical REC projects shown to them in the DCE. Yet, the coefficient is not statistically significant at conventional levels. However, participants chose the opt-out option in only 10% of all choice sets. Since participants saw eight choice sets each, the opt-out option was chosen in less than one choice set, on average.

Table 9: Results of mixed logit model for DCE on participation in renewable energy cooperatives

	France
Mean	
<i>status_quo</i>	-0.2479 (0.272)
<i>rate</i>	0.3123*** (0.026)
<i>municip</i>	-0.0734 (0.052)
<i>firms</i>	-0.3611*** (0.091)
<i>cap_cont</i>	-0.5413*** (0.075)
<i>delegate</i>	0.2849*** (0.051)
<i>self35</i>	0.9501*** (0.067)
<i>self70</i>	1.3923*** (0.086)
Standard deviation	
<i>status_quo</i>	-6.3340*** (0.371)
<i>rate</i>	0.4467*** (0.026)
<i>municip</i>	-0.1343 (0.166)
<i>firms</i>	0.5238*** (0.141)
<i>cap_cont</i>	-1.1403*** (0.074)
<i>delegate</i>	-0.5490*** (0.072)
<i>self35</i>	0.1137 (0.138)
<i>self70</i>	0.9915*** (0.089)
Model	
LL	-5,849.153
Participants	1,022
Observations	24,528

Standard errors in parentheses; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

For *rate*, we find a positive and statistically significant coefficient implying that participants prefer projects with a higher rate of return. This finding is in line with the extant literature in similar contexts (e.g. Vuichard et al., 2019; Pons-Seres de Brauwer and Cohen, 2020; Cohen et al., 2021). It is further supported by findings analysing additional items in the questionnaire. As part of the survey, we also asked participants about the most important criteria they would apply if they were to make a financial investment. They could pick up to three from a list of 10 criteria comprising of financial returns, financial risk, liquidity, environmental criteria, social/ethical criteria, type of product the investment finances, benefits to the local community where the project is implemented, participation in decision on how funds are distributed, transaction costs, a good understanding about the products/services/technology the investment finances. Accordingly, financial return is the most important criteria ($p < 0.01$).

The negative coefficient for *municip* suggests that on average, participants dislike RECs where municipalities may own parts of the shares compared to a REC where only citizens may own shares, yet the coefficient is not statistically significant at conventional levels. Similarly, but statistically significantly, participants appear to strongly dislike firms' financial involvement in RECs. This finding supports earlier findings by Ek and Persson (2014), Brennan and Rensburg (2020) and Cohen et al. (2021). Based on a Wald test, we conclude that participants prefer municipalities to firms owning shares of a REC. To allow for a more substantive interpretation of the results reported in Table 9, we calculate the estimated marginal willingness to pay for attributes based on equation (5). In our case, willingness to pay is measured as a percentage point change in the rate of return (see Table 10). Accordingly, for the average participant the rate of return would have to be about 1.2 percentage points higher if firms were allowed to own shares of a REC compared to a situation where only citizens were allowed to own shares.

The findings for *cap_cont* imply that on average participants prefer a one-member-one-vote rule to a rule where voting rights are based on the capital contribution. This result is in line with a similar finding by Sagebiel et al. (2014). As Table 10 implies, for the average participant the 'cost' of a capital-based voting rule compared to a one-member-one-vote rule would be about 1.7 percentage points of the rate of return.

Our findings for *delegate* suggest that on average participants prefer to have the possibility to delegate their voting rights to a proxy rather than having to participate personally in the general assembly. To this end, participants are willing to give up 0.9 percentage points of the rate of return on their investment. This finding suggests that for the average participant in our sample the transaction costs associated with participating in these meetings typically outweigh the benefits of active involvement in the governance of the REC. This finding is also supported by Figure 3, which implies that factors such as 'having a say in local power generation issues' or 'being part in a local initiative' do not rank very highly compared to receiving financial benefits or supporting renewable energy production.

Figure 3: Factors which would motivate participants to invest in a renewable energy cooperative as shares of participants (%) selecting a particular factor (participants could select up to three factors)

Finally, our results for the coefficients associated with *self35* and *self70* mean that participants prefer higher shares of self-consumption. Because in our experiment self-consumption of electricity is assumed to leave the electricity bill unchanged, this result suggests that on average, participants enjoy non-monetary benefits from using the electricity generated by 'their' REC. According to Table 10, these non-monetary benefits are rather substantial. On average, participants are willing to give up about 3 percentage points of the rate of return to be able to self-consume 35% of their household's electricity consumption. They are willing to give up about 4.5 percentage points of the rate of return to self-consume 70% of their household's electricity consumption.¹³ Hence, participants appear to exhibit decreasing non-monetary returns to shares of self-consumption. The results in Figure 3 also suggest that participants have strong preferences for self-consumption. 'Gaining autonomy from energy suppliers' ranks among the top three factors that would motivate participants to invest in a REC. Similarly, when asked in the survey whether they would like to be more independent from their current energy provider, about 31% agreed or fully agreed.

Table 10: Estimated willingness-to-pay for attributes of renewable energy cooperatives (measured as a percentage point change in the rate of return)

<i>firms</i>	-1.156
<i>cap_cont</i>	-1.733
<i>delegate</i>	0.912
<i>self35</i>	3.042
<i>self70</i>	4.458

4.4 Conclusions

Our findings from analysing the DCE in France on participation in RECs via a standard mixed logit model suggest that on average, participants prefer RECs with a higher rate of return, which are only owned by citizens and possibly municipalities, where decisions are made based on a one-member-one-vote rule (rather than based on the capital contribution), where delegation of voting rights to a proxy is possible, and which allow for high shares of self-consumption of the electricity generated by the REC. Non-monetary benefits from self-consuming electricity appear to be high, and to decrease with the shares of self-consumption. These findings provide valuable

¹³ We also estimated coefficients and WTP values excluding those participants who failed to provide a correct answer to the comprehension question on self-consumption. Within the subsample of participants who correctly answered the comprehension question, we find lower but still substantial WTP values: participants are willing to give up about 2.1 (3.0) percentage points of the rate of return to be able to self-consume 35% (70%) of their household's electricity consumption.

guidance for the design of business models of RECs, which will be further discussed in Deliverable D5.4.

5 DCE ON ENERGY GAMIFICATION THROUGH MOBILE APPLICATIONS (GERMANY)

In this section, we present the discrete choice experiment (DCE) carried out in Germany on energy gamification through mobile applications (apps). In recent years, the number of mobile apps that encourage users to change their energy behaviours has been increasing. Many of these apps include gamification or serious game components to increase user engagement and salience of behavioural changes (Beck et al., 2019; Mulcahy et al. 2020). Through our DCE, we aim to better understand individual preferences for game design elements (namely social comparison and competition) in energy apps relative to preferences for other app features, different app developers and subscription fees.

In the following sub-sections, we first provide more details on the sample of participants in the DCE. Then we describe the DCE design, and report and discuss the results.

5.1 Survey

In Germany, 1,011 participants who indicated that they used a smartphone or tablet at least occasionally completed the DCE on gamification through mobile apps.¹⁴ Summary statistics for the sample are presented in Table 11 next to national population statistics for comparison. Overall, sample statistics are close to national statistics, though participants between 30 and 49 years are overrepresented compared to other age categories.

Table 11: Sample characteristics for participants in the DCE on gamification through mobile applications

	Sample	Population
Share of males^a	48.3	49.3%
Age (share of adult population)^b		
18-29	14.2%	16.5%
30-49	37.9%	30.3%
50-64	24.4%	27.3%
65 and older	23.4%	25.8%
Household income		
2,000 EUR or less ^c	29.5%	30%
2,001 – 3,600 EUR	31.1%	31%
More than 3,600 EUR	39.5%	39%

^a Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: Statistisches Bundesamt (2018).

¹⁴ In total, 70 participants indicated never using a smartphone or tablet and were thus not eligible to take part in the DCE on gamification through mobile apps.

5.2 DCE design

To introduce the DCE on energy gamification through mobile apps, we used the following framing:¹⁵

*"On the following pages, we will show you different mobile apps to help you save energy in your daily life, participate in energy challenges, or inform you about projects and initiatives in the energy sector. We would like to know **which of these mobile apps you would like to use** if they were available to you.*

You may assume that all mobile apps presented to you are compatible with your mobile phone's operating system and are updated regularly.

*The mobile apps shown to you **all offer energy saving tips and allow you to track your electricity consumption to see how it increases or decreases over time.** If your home is equipped with a smart electricity meter, the app can be paired with the smart electricity meter and track your electricity consumption automatically. If your home is not equipped with a smart electricity meter, the app allows you to scan your electricity meter with your mobile phone."*

Participants were then asked to make a series of choice decisions between different mobile apps which differed by the following attributes

1. **Developer:** The mobile apps have either been developed by the participant's city or region, by a national public agency, or by the participant's electricity provider.
2. **Expert advice:** Some of the apps offer the possibility to exchange with energy experts to help identify the most effective ways to save energy on a daily basis.
3. **Compare and compete with other households:** Some mobile apps allow participants to compare their electricity consumption to the electricity consumption of similar households, while other mobile apps allow participants to take part in online challenges and compete against other households to reduce electricity consumption.
4. **Annual subscription fee:** The annual subscription fee to use the apps ranges from 10 cents to 6€.
5. **Use of subscription fees:** For some apps, the provider donates 50% of the annual subscription fees to fund nature conservation measures in the participant's region or to support low-income households in the participant's region.

The attributes and levels used in the DCE are shown in Table 12.

¹⁵ Instructions highlighted in 'bold' were also seen highlighted in 'bold' by participants.

Table 12: Levels of different attributes considered in the DCE on energy gamification through mobile applications

Attribute	Levels	Variable	Type
Developer	your city or region, national public agency, your electricity provider;	(baseline) <i>agency provider</i>	dummy dummy
Expert advice	no, yes;	(baseline) <i>advice</i>	dummy
Compare and compete with other households	no, compare your electricity consumption to similar households, participate in online challenges and compete against similar households;	(baseline) <i>compare</i> <i>compete</i>	dummy dummy
Annual subscription fee	10 cents, 2 EUR, 4 EUR, 6 EUR;	<i>fee</i>	continuous
Use of subscription fee	no donation, 50% are donated to finance nature conservation measures in your region, 50% are donated to support low-income households in your region;	(baseline) <i>nature lowincome</i>	dummy dummy

As in the previous DCEs, we employed a Bayesian-efficient design (Sándor and Wedel, 2001) to limit the number of choice sets shown to participants and to increase the efficiency of the DCE design. The priors used for the design were obtained from a second pre-test with 50 participants in the UK using Prolific Academic. The final DCE consisted of 24 choice sets divided into 3 blocks. In each choice set, participants were shown two mobile apps that differed in the attributes described above. Figure 4 shows an example of a choice set used in the DCE.

Which of the following mobile apps would you like to download?

Please consider thoroughly that you actually are willing to download the mobile app when making your decisions.

	Mobile app A	Mobile app B
Developer	your city or region	national public agency
Expert advice	yes	no
Compare and compete with other households	no	compare your electricity consumption to similar households
Annual subscription fee	2 €	4 €
Use of subscription fee	no donation	50% are donated to support low-income households in your region

Mobile app A Mobile app B None of these mobile apps

I would like to download:

Figure 4: Example of a choice set in the DCE on gamification through mobile applications

To mitigate hypothetical bias in the DCE, we included again a cheap talk design: Prior to each choice task, participants were asked to consider thoroughly that they were actually willing to download the mobile app when making their decisions. Moreover, participants always had the possibility to choose an opt-out option, i.e. to not select any of the mobile apps presented to them.

Our choice of attributes and attribute levels was guided by the literature studying individual motives to download and use mobile apps related to energy consumption and behaviours. Participants were assumed to make trade-offs between the attributes based on their preferences for specific features of the mobile apps, including nudging and gamification components, the type of developer and annual subscription fees.

Nudges, i.e. subtle changes in decision contexts that lead to predictable behavioural changes of imperfectly rational individuals, have become a popular policy tool following in particular the works of Thaler and Sunstein (Thaler and Sunstein, 2003; Sunstein and Thaler, 2003, Thaler and Sunstein 2008). In environmental policy, so called 'green nudges' that aim at promoting pro-environmental behaviour are discussed and implemented increasingly frequently by policy-makers (see for example Schubert (2017) for a review on green nudges and their effectiveness). Many of these green nudges target changes in households' energy consumption behaviours, for example through changes in default electricity contracts (e.g. Pichert and Katsikopoulos, 2008; Sunstein and Reisch, 2014, Kaiser et al. 2020) or regular feedback on energy consumption (e.g., Seligman and Darley, 1977; Karlim et al., 2015; Aydin et al., 2018). Relating households' own energy consumption to the consumption of other households, in particular, has been shown to lead to energy savings (Allcott, 2011; Allcott and Rogers, 2014, Allcott and Kessler, 2019), though there is mixed evidence regarding the effectiveness of social comparison feedback in the absence of direct monetary incentives (Myers and Souza, 2020; Kandul et al., 2020). In our DCE, we did not test the effectiveness of social comparison feedback directly but rather investigated whether the availability of social comparison feedback increases the propensity to purchase an energy app. For this purpose, we included comparison with similar households as an attribute level in our DCE. We expected that participants are eager to take part in social comparison – albeit to varying degrees (Gibbons and Buunk, 1999) – and thus generally prefer options that offer social comparison feedback over options that do not.

For some options, instead of including social comparison feedback as a feature of the mobile app, we included an alternative gamification component that involves competing with other households through the mobile app. The literature investigating the impact of different gamification components in mobile apps that target energy behaviours is still nascent. Early research suggests that game elements can positively impact enjoyment of energy apps and enhance behavioural changes, with challenges being particularly effective (Mulcahy, et al. 2020). Beck et al. (2019) find that gamification has a positive effect on user ratings of energy apps, but that gamification components other than feedback (e.g. challenges, leader boards, badges) remain largely underutilized in energy apps. Against this background, we investigate if the option to compete with similar households increases participants' propensity to purchase a mobile app, compared to social comparison feedback or to no gamification components.

The attribute expert advice was selected among three attributes that represented additional, non-gamified features of a mobile app related to energy behaviours. The other two attributes we

had considered were ‘customizable reminders’¹⁶ and ‘information on participatory eco-initiatives’¹⁷. The three attributes had been identified based on discussions with SONNET researchers and a review of existing energy apps. A pre-test with 50 participants in the UK using the platform Prolific Academic showed that participants paid considerably more attention to the attribute expert advice compared to the two other attributes. We thus kept expert advice as an attribute in the DCE. The other two attributes were dropped in order to keep the choice tasks sufficiently simple.

Participants’ propensity to purchase a mobile app may also depend on the identity of the app developer. In our DCE, we considered three different types of developers: cities or regions, national public agencies, and utilities. National public agencies may develop energy apps as part of the digital tools used by governments to support national energy efficiency policy strategies (IEA, 2021). Similarly, cities or regions can use mobile apps to help them achieve sustainability goals through (long-term) engagement of citizens by means of gamification (Kazhamiakin et al. 2016). Finally, utilities use mobile apps to improve customer experience (see e.g. Moreno-Munoz et al., 2016; Mulcahy et al. 2020). Among other features, these apps most frequently include personalized support and energy saving tips (Moreno-Munoz et al., 2016) as well as consumption feedback (Beck et al., 2019). Preferences for different app developers may for instance be driven by trust. Przepiorka and Horne (2018) find that trust mediates the effects of utility companies’ behaviour on consumers’ willingness to use an energy app provided by the utility. In general, by using an energy app, consumers are giving consent that the app collects and processes certain information on household characteristics and behaviours, including, for example, energy consumption data. Giving consent for the use of energy data can be seen as an expression of trust (Véliz and Grunewald, 2018). Thus, if an app developer is considered less trustworthy, we would expect to observe a lower willingness to download the energy app.

Finally, we included a cost attribute in form of a yearly subscription fee in order to observe trade-offs between the attributes described above and costs. To avoid that those participants with low willingness-to-pay disengage from our DCE, we further included a charitable donation attribute: in some cases, 50% of the subscription fees is donated either to fund nature conservation measures or to support low-income households. In the literature, such charity incentives have been found to increase consumers’ willingness to pay for different products (e.g. Strahilevitz, 1999; Koschate-Fischer et al. 2012).

¹⁶ In the pre-test, the attribute was described to participants as follows: “Some of the apps send you reminders on what you could do to decrease your energy consumption (e.g. switch off the light or turn down the heat in rooms you do not currently use, turn off or unplug appliances that are not currently in use, etc.). You can customize the type of reminders you want to receive and how frequently you want to receive them (e.g. daily, weekly, ...).”

¹⁷ In the pre-test, the attribute was described to participants as follows: “Some mobile apps provide information on participatory eco-initiatives in your region and how you can get involved if you wish to (e.g. citizen or neighbourhood initiatives to save energy or other resources, raise awareness for the environment, ...).”

5.3 Results

We estimated the following specification of the mixed logit model in equation (8):

$$U_{njt} = \beta_{1n}status_quo + \beta_{2n}agency + \beta_{3n}provider + \beta_{4n}compare + \beta_{5n}compete + \beta_{6n}advice + \beta_{7n}fee + \beta_{8n}nature + \beta_{9n}lowincome + \varepsilon_{njt}, \quad (8)$$

The specification includes the variables for the DCE attributes and levels described in Table 12. In addition, *status_quo* is a dummy variable that takes on the value one for the opt-out option in each choice set and zero for all other choice alternatives.

The results of estimating the mixed logit model in equation (8) appear in Table 13. Looking first at the lower part of Table 13 which displays the standard deviations of the parameter estimates we note that all estimates of the standard deviations are statistically significant. This finding suggests heterogeneity in attribute preferences across participants and corroborates our use of a mixed logit model to analyse the data obtained from the DCE. The upper part of Table 13 reports the mean estimate of the coefficients of the (latent) utility function in equation (8). Accordingly, all coefficients associated with the attributes in the DCE, except the coefficient for *provider*, are statistically significant.

The positive and significant coefficient for *status_quo* in the upper part of Table 13 suggests that on average participants prefer not to download a mobile app. We thus observe generally low interest in the SIE. More precisely, participants would need to receive on average 3.72 EUR per year to use a free app developed by their city or region and with none of the features described in the DCE (see Table 14).

The positive and statistically significant coefficients for *compare* and *compete* indicate that on average participants value these mobile app features, which is consistent with previous findings in the literature (Mulcahy et al, 2020, Beck et al. 2019). Similarly, the positive and significant coefficient for *advice* indicates that participant propensity to download an app increases if expert advice is included as a feature. The similar magnitudes of all three coefficients further indicate that social comparison, competition, and expert advice have similar effects on participant propensity to choose a mobile app.

Table 13: Results of mixed logit model for DCE on participation in gamification through mobile applications

	Germany
Mean	
<i>status_quo</i>	1.6460*** (0.195)
<i>agency</i>	-0.2217*** (0.068)
<i>provider</i>	0.0419 (0.091)
<i>compare</i>	0.4956*** (0.100)
<i>compete</i>	0.4862*** (0.089)
<i>advice</i>	0.5019*** (0.063)
<i>fee</i>	-0.4429*** (0.029)
<i>nature</i>	0.8969*** (0.102)
<i>lowincome</i>	0.8517*** (0.089)
Standard deviation	
<i>status_quo</i>	5.3732*** (0.272)
<i>agency</i>	0.5182*** (0.139)
<i>provider</i>	0.8771*** (0.126)
<i>compare</i>	0.6932*** (0.153)
<i>compete</i>	1.0753*** (0.114)
<i>advice</i>	0.7430*** (0.092)
<i>fee</i>	0.4731*** (0.028)
<i>nature</i>	1.0964*** (0.118)
<i>lowincome</i>	0.8579*** (0.118)
Log likelihood	-5,326.468
Participants	1,011
Observations	24,264

Standard errors in parentheses; * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

The negative and significant coefficient for *agency* indicates that on average participants prefer mobile apps developed by their city or region over mobile apps developed by national public agencies. In contrast, we observe no difference, on average, between preferences for apps developed by the participant's city or region and apps developed by the participant's energy supplier.

The coefficient for *fee* is – as expected – negative and statistically significant, indicating that participant's dislike mobile apps with higher annual subscription fees. This is also consistent with the finding that almost half of the participants indicate in a follow-up survey question that they have never spent money on a mobile app. At the same time, the positive and significant

coefficients for *nature* and *lowincome* suggest that participants are more willing to download a mobile app if part of the subscription fees is donated to either finance nature conservation measures or support low-income households – a finding consistent with extant literature (Strahilevitz, 1999; Koschate-Fischer et al. 2012). Yet, in contrast to results from the DCE on investment projects in renewable electricity generation, comparing the coefficients for *lowincome* and *nature* using a Wald test, we find no difference in preferences between donations to support low-income households and donations to fund nature conservation measures.

Table 14: Estimated willingness-to-pay for status quo and attributes of mobile apps (measured in EUR per year)

<i>status_quo</i>	3.72
<i>agency</i>	-0.50
<i>compare</i>	1.12
<i>compete</i>	1.10
<i>advice</i>	1.13
<i>nature</i>	2.03
<i>lowincome</i>	1.92

5.4 Conclusions

Our findings from analysing the DCE in Germany on gamification through mobile apps via a standard mixed logit model suggest that on average, participants are reluctant to download energy apps. Higher annual subscription fees further decrease participant's propensity to download a mobile app unless a share of the subscription fees is donated to fund nature conservation measures or to support low-income households. The coefficients for *nature* and *lowincome* are approximately twice the size of the coefficient for *fee*, indicating that charitable donations can more than offset the negative effects of subscription fees¹⁸. App features including nudges (social comparison) and gamification components (competitions) as well as expert advice all have positive effects of similar magnitude on participants' willingness to download a mobile app. These results provide initial insights into the potential of mobile apps to engage citizens in the energy transition and support behavioural change.

¹⁸ In our DCE, for the average participant, charitable donations of 50% of the subscription fees have the same effect on utility as a decrease in subscription fees by 2 EUR per year. Our DCE, however, does not allow to predict how participants would react to charitable donations that are associated with more expensive products or services than the mobile apps considered in the DCE.

6 EXPERIMENT ON CAMPAIGNS AGAINST SPECIFIC ENERGY PATHWAYS (POLAND)

In this section, we present the experiment carried out in Poland on campaigns against specific energy pathways. First, we provide more details on the surveys and the sample. Then we describe the experimental design, and report and discuss the results. For this SIE-field a different experimental approach was used. Instead of using a discrete choice experiment (DCE), an information treatment including three types of information was designed.

6.1 Survey

Overall, 2,102 participants from Poland took part in our study and half of them were randomly assigned either to the DCE on decentralized electricity generation (see chapter 3) or the here described experiment on campaigns against specific energy pathways. 1,158 participants completed this experiment, however, as participants were excluded as speeders if they needed less than 1/3 of the median response time the final sample consists of 1,124 participants. Across the three experimental conditions the number of speeders is not significantly different (tested via Chi-square test, $p < 0.05$) and the three groups are of similar size.

Table 15: Sample characteristics across treatment groups for participants in the experiment on campaigns against specific energy pathways

	T1	T2	T3	Sign.	Overall	Population
Participants	384	373	367		1,124	
Share of males^a	50.0%	43.7%	53.1%	*	48.9%	48.4%
Age (share of adult population)^b						
18-29	12.8%	14.7%	17.2%		14.9%	17.4%
30-49	38.0%	39.4%	35.4%		37.6%	36.9%
50-64	24.2%	25.5%	22.9%		24.2%	24.1%
65 and older	25.0%	20.4%	24.5%		23.3%	21.6%
Household income						
3,000 PLN or less ^c	22.7%	24.1%	19.9%		22.2%	30%
3,001 – 5,900 PLN	43.5%	43.2%	43.6%		43.4%	40%
More than 5,900 PLN	33.9%	32.7%	36.5%		34.3%	30%

Note: Source of population statistics: ^a Eurostat (2020). ^b Source of population statistics: Eurostat (2019). ^c Source of population statistics: ESS (2020). Treatment groups: T1=Innovation, T2=Health and Environment, T3=National interest (see more details below).

Overall, the sample is fairly similar to the Polish population in terms of gender and age but with an underrepresentation of the lowest income category. Regarding the randomisation between experimental treatments, Chi²-tests point out that there is no difference with regard to age, but that the number of male / female participants is not the same between conditions. As can be seen from the percentages in the table, fewer men were part of the second treatment.

6.2 Experimental design

The experimental design for the experiment on campaigns against specific energy pathways is displayed in Figure 5. While Poland's energy sector is still dominated by producing electricity from coal, and coal mining still plays a relevant role in terms of employment, prior research has pointed out that Polish citizens tend to favour electricity generation from renewable energy (Wojciechowska-Solis and Soroka 2018; Wojciechowska-Solis 2018). Against this background, the support for a campaign claiming an earlier coal phase-out in favour of increasing domestic renewables was chosen as a scenario for the experiment. The research goal was to analyse in how far different lines of argument elicit different levels of support.

Figure 5: Overview of experimental design on specific energy pathways

The three lines of argument were presented as a fictitious news item and differed on the aspects stressed. Each participant only received one of the three versions.

The following questions will refer to the production of energy from coal and alternative energy pathways relying on domestic renewable energy sources.

Please imagine that you see the following news item.

Campaign launched for a coal exit strategy

Last week a campaign was launched by a coalition of several organisations. The aim of the campaign is to demand that Poland shifts from energy production from coal to domestic renewable energy sources until 2030.

The organisers of the protest emphasized that this is a question of preparing Poland for the future. Such an **innovation pathway** will contribute to societal economic benefits like the creation of employment and support schemes from the EU are available for the transition.

Campaign launched for a coal exit strategy

Last week a campaign was launched by a coalition of several organisations. The aim of the campaign is to demand that Poland shifts from energy production from coal to domestic renewable energy sources until 2030.

The organisers of the protest emphasized that this is a question of increasing health and environmental standards in Poland. Such an **environmental pathway** will contribute to mitigate negative impacts on citizen's health and on nature.

Campaign launched for a coal exit strategy

Last week a campaign was launched by a coalition of several organisations. The aim of the campaign is to demand that Poland shifts from energy production from coal to domestic renewable energy sources until 2030.

The organisers of the protest emphasized that this is a question of national interest for Poland. Such an **energy security pathway** will increase energy security by sustaining independence from energy imports.

Figure 6: Different information treatments. On top: innovation pathway (T1). Middle: environmental pathway (T2). Bottom: energy security pathway (T3).

The three lines of argument were chosen based on lines of argument discussed around the Polish energy transition in the academic literature. For example, Badera and Kocoń (2014) argue around energy security in an analysis on the local acceptance of lignite mining. Osička et al. (2020) conduct a media analysis on the Polish discourse on the coal industry identifying arguments related to local environment, phase-out management, competitiveness, climate, and employment as the most frequent ones (see also Deliverable 3.2 on case studies in Poland).

Following this information, participants were asked (see Table 16 for the single items):

- ▲ about their emotional response to the described campaign using three opposing pairs of adjectives

- ▲ about the extent the arguments provided are regarded as credible and whether they expect such a campaign to be successful
- ▲ how likely they would engage in a range of activities if they heard about such a campaign in real life ranging from looking for further information to participating in events or donating money or showing opposition to such a campaign

These blocks of questions aimed at measuring the influence of the information treatment. Before leaving the survey, it was emphasised again that the campaign alluded to was fictitious.

This was followed by further questions on the energy transition in Poland, more specifically a coal phase-out. Participants were asked about:

- ▲ their overall opinion on whether Poland should shift from coal to domestic renewable energy. See Figure 7 for the wording of this question.
- ▲ perceived consequences of such a phase-out. See Table 17 for more details on the wording of the items.
- ▲ their personal relation to the coal industry and the energy transition. See Table 18 for more details on the wording of the items.

6.3 Descriptive findings and data preparation

Table 16 provides an overview on the relevant descriptive statistics. For items within the same block that referred to the same set of perceptions like the emotional response to the campaign, it was tested whether the items could be aggregated into one scale or if it made more sense to analyse them separately. This included the estimation of the internal consistency (Cronbach's α) as well as an inspection via an exploratory factor analysis. In case of a one-factor solution in the factor analysis, an internal consistency above 0.7, and no items reducing the internal consistency, items were aggregated into one scale. Scales and remaining single items were z-standardized for further multivariate analysis.

As can be seen from Table 16, on average, participants showed a (slightly) positive emotional response to the campaigns presented as the mean values are in the upper part of the answering scale.¹⁹ The average rating for the argument credibility and the likelihood for success are also in the supporting part of the answering scale. The answering patterns are more mixed for behavioural intentions triggered by the campaigns - overall participants indicated a tendency to look for further information, but behaviour requiring more time and personal effort like participating in events or donating money received average ratings in the lower part of the

¹⁹ This scale as well as the items on credibility and success and the scale on behavioural intentions were found to be significantly ($p < 0.01$) different from the mid-point 3 of the response scale as corroborated by t-tests.

answering scale. The reverse worded item referring to showing opposition received the lowest ratings and was also not consistent with the other items.

Table 16: Descriptive statistics for scales and items around the information treatment

Scale / item	Mean (SD)	Cronbach's α (no of items)
Emotional response to campaign	3.84 (1.19)	.91 (3 items)
<i>Feeling negative vs. positive</i>	3.93 (1.31)	
<i>Feeling uncomfortable vs. comfortable</i>	3.74 (1.30)	
<i>Feeling uninterested vs. interested</i>	3.88 (1.28)	
Arguments from campaign credible	3.51 (1.25)	
Campaign likely to be successful	3.31 (1.17)	
Behavioural intentions on campaign	2.77 (1.09)	.87 (5 items)
<i>Look for further information</i>	3.42 (1.29)	
<i>Share information about campaign</i>	2.82 (1.42)	
<i>Sign petition in support</i>	3.14 (1.48)	
<i>Participate in an event</i>	2.38 (1.28)	
<i>Donate money</i>	2.11 (1.23)	
<i>Show opposition*</i>	2.08 (1.32)	

Note. Responses were given on 5-point-Likert-scales with higher values signifying support / positive evaluations. Items in italics are the single items included in the scale shown directly above. Items with an * were part of the same question block but not included in the scale as they reduced scale reliability.

After the questions on the campaign, participants were asked about their overall personal opinion on an earlier coal phase-out in Poland by 2030 and a shift to renewable energies instead. The majority of participants was sceptical about such a proposal with 54% answering 'definitely no' or 'rather no' while the share of those answering 'rather yes' or 'yes' adds up to 32% while 14% answer 'don't know' (see Figure 7).

Figure 7: Participants' personal opinion on whether Poland should shift from coal to domestic renewable energy by 2030

We further analyse items eliciting participants' expected consequences of an earlier coal phase-out. These items took up the arguments used in the experimental treatments. The highest support was associated with the arguments in relation to positive impacts on nature and health followed by the arguments around innovativeness while energy security and independence from imports were seen as less relevant. The least support was received by the statement that an earlier phase-out would have more negative than positive consequences. Tests on the significance between the ratings (ANOVA for repeated measures) point out that most of the ratings differ significantly from each other in a statistical sense.

Table 17: Descriptive statistics for the consequences of an earlier coal phase-out in Poland

Scale / item	Mean (SD)	Cronbach's α (no of items)
Evaluation of consequences of an earlier coal phase-out	3.54 (1.11)	.95 (6 items)
<i>...make country more innovative economically</i>	3.36 (1.27)	
<i>...make country more innovative by EU-support</i>	3.56 (1.25)	
<i>...will increase health</i>	3.75 (1.23)	
<i>...will have positive impact on nature</i>	3.86 (1.23)	
<i>...will increase energy security</i>	3.35 (1.26)	
<i>...will increase independence from imports</i>	3.35 (1.26)	
<i>...will have more negative than positive impacts*</i>	2.67 (1.33)	

Note. Responses were given on 5-point-Likert-scales with higher values signifying support / positive evaluations. Items in italics are the single items included in the scale shown directly above. Items with an * were part of the same question block but not included in the scale as they reduced scale reliability.

A further list of questions referred to the personal relation and engagement with coal, the coal industry and the energy transition.

Table 18: Personal relation and engagement with the coal industry and the energy transition.

Item	Responses in %
Live near (<50 km) of facilities for mining/ coal energy?	Yes: 23.9
Self or family engaged with coal industry?	Yes: 7.3
Engaged with future of coal?	Yes for earlier phase-out: 5.4 Yes to keep coal: 4.4
Energy transition part of work?	Yes: 7.8
Family member engaged with energy transition?	Yes: 9.4
Heating home with coal?	Yes: 33.9 In the past: 17.8
Received subsidies for exchanging coal heating?	Yes: 12.5

The answers show that nearly a quarter of the sample lives in regions with the presence of mining and/or the coal industry as well as a third is heating their homes with coal. Political engagement or working with the energy transition applies to smaller shares.

6.4 Findings from the experiment

6.4.1 Direct influence of the experimental conditions

The main research question for the experiment is whether the different treatments have an effect on the participants' perceptions and behavioural intentions. We use analysis of variance (ANOVA) to directly test the influence of the experimental treatment conditions on the dependent variables referring to perceptions and intentions on the information treatment. ANOVAs test for differences in continuous variables (dependent variable) along the categories of a qualitative variable (independent variable), i.e. in our case if the ratings by the participants differ from each other between the three treatments. We use a multivariate ANOVA (MANOVA) that simultaneously tests several dependent variables considering the interplay between the dependent variables as well as controlling for an accumulation of alpha-errors. In the following, we present two MANOVAs, one using the single items from Table 16 ("Single item MANOVA") and one building on the scales ("Scale MANOVA") as one of the preconditions for MANOVA is to avoid high multi-collinearity.²⁰ Further preconditions were also examined: identification of outliers via box-plots (no outliers identified), normal distribution (this condition was violated, however, due to the robustness of MANOVA towards this condition and given the high sample size we continued with the analysis).

We estimate two MANOVAs: The first one employs the single items. This leads to a significant overall model with $F(22, 2222) = 1.557, p < .05$, partial $\eta^2 = .015$, Wilk's $\Lambda = .970$. The second model uses the scores on the emotional response and the behavioural intentions instead of the single items and leads to a model significant on the $p < 0.1$ -level with $F(8, 2236) = 1.748, p < 0.10$, partial $\eta^2 = .006$, Wilk's $\Lambda = .988$. These omnibus tests, however, do not give an indication which conditions and variables are significantly different from each other. To specify this between subject tests were employed. These lead to a nearly significant (i.e. $p < 0.1$) finding in one case only, namely a difference in how far participants felt uninterested/interested in the information from the treatment. The specific post-hoc-test (Tukey-HSD) then fails to be statistically significant (see Table 19). Table 19 also provides the descriptive statistics for all dependent variables in the three conditions.

Thus, overall, the results do not point to significant differences between the three treatments. Possibly, effects become statistically significant once additional variables are considered to control for heterogeneity and hence reduce the variance. We make a first attempt in this direction by estimating regression models in the next section.

²⁰ The literature provides different values as indicating multi-collinearity; most authors propose bivariate correlations below .8 or .9 to avoid multi-collinearity.

Table 19: Influence of the experimental conditions: means and SD for all dependent variables in the three treatment groups.

Scale / item	Mean (SD)			Between-subject
	T1	T2	T3	
Emotional response to campaign	3.77 (1.21)	3.95 (1.15)	3.84 (1.19)	
<i>Feeling negative vs. positive</i>	3.88 (1.30)	4.03 (1.26)	3.88 (1.35)	
<i>Feeling uncomfortable vs. comfortable</i>	3.66 (1.33)	3.85 (1.24)	3.71 (1.31)	
<i>Feeling uninterested vs. interested</i>	3.76 (1.32)	3.95 (1.24)	3.93 (1.26)	*
Arguments from campaign credible	3.48 (1.31)	3.55 (1.23)	3.51 (1.22)	
Campaign likely to be successful	3.32 (1.18)	3.26 (1.17)	3.35 (1.17)	
Behavioural intentions on campaign	2.72 (1.07)	2.80 (1.10)	2.81 (1.11)	
<i>Look for further information</i>	3.48 (1.30)	3.37 (1.26)	3.42 (1.31)	
<i>Share information about campaign</i>	2.76 (1.43)	2.85 (1.42)	2.84 (1.41)	
<i>Sign petition in support</i>	3.06 (1.47)	3.19 (1.5)	3.17 (1.47)	
<i>Participate in an event</i>	2.29 (1.29)	2.40 (1.29)	2.47 (1.27)	
<i>Donate money</i>	2.01 (1.21)	2.16 (1.26)	2.18 (1.22)	
<i>Show opposition[†]</i>	2.06 (1.33)	2.13 (1.33)	2.06 (1.31)	

Note. T1=Innovation, T2=Health and Environment, T3=National interest; Responses were given on 5-point-Likert-scales with higher values signifying support / positive evaluations. Items marked with [†] are not part of summarizing scale. * - p<0.10, ** - p<0.05, *** - p<0.01.

6.4.2 Further exploratory analyses of treatment influence

Potential influence from the three treatments is further analysed focusing on the emotional response as a dependent variable. We estimate stepwise linear regression models²¹ entering dummy variables for the experimental conditions (Step 1), controlling for socio-demographic criteria (Step 2), indicators around the involvement with the coal industry (Step 3), identification with a variety of political views (Step 4), identification with Poland and the EU (Step 5) as well as items on the credibility/expected success for the campaign (Step 6). For step 3 those variables

²¹ By running OLS models we implicitly assume that the variables obtained from Likert-scaled items can be treated as interval variables, which is common practice in psychology. Otherwise, ordered response models would need to be employed.

from Table 18 were chosen where more than a small group (>15%) has ticked 'yes'. As an earlier coal phase-out is a political decision, the variables in Step 4 were seen as potentially relevant.

At the bottom of Table 20, R and the increase in R^2 are indicated. It turns out that the model only becomes significant in the third step and then every block of variables added significantly increases the share of variance explained. The full models each result in a high share of variance explained with 0.625 for the score measure and values >0.480 for the single items.

Comparing across the four models, we find highly similar patterns of (in-)significant effects with the one relying on the scale as dependent variable as the most comprehensive, in the sense that regression coefficients as well as the share of variance explained tend to be higher than in the single-item model.

For the final model, it turns out that participants who read the arguments referring to improvements for the environment and public health (T2) were significantly more likely to show a positive emotional response than participants who were exposed to the innovation pathway treatment (T1), which serves as the baseline treatment. Similarly, we find the effect of T2 on the emotional response to be stronger than the effect of T3 (national energy security pathway). In comparison, we fail to find a difference between the treatment referring to national interest (T3) and T1 (innovation pathway).

The socio-demographic variables do not seem to play a major role, only age is significantly and negatively related to the dependent variable, i.e. younger people are more likely to show a more positive response to the campaign. The variables on prior experience with coal also have some influence, especially the aggregated scale on the consequences of an earlier phase-out and the preference for coal as an energy source, but partly also whether people are using coal for heating.

Identification with environmentally-oriented policies is consistently significantly positively related to the emotional response. For three of the four regression models we find also a significant negative influence from identification with conservative policies.

Finally, the items whether the campaign is expected to be successful and whether the arguments presented were seen as credible are also strong predictors.

Table 20: Regression analyses considering the treatment influence on emotional response

<i>Dependent variable</i>	<i>Emotional Response Score</i>		<i>Negative - positive</i>		<i>Uncomfortable vs. comfortable</i>		<i>Uninterested vs. interested</i>	
	<i>Beta</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Step 1								
Dummy Experiment T2	.066	***	.055	**	.060	***	.065	**
Dummy Experiment T3	-.003		-.025		-.012		.030	
Step 2								
Gender (1=male)	.028		.026		-.008		.045	
Age (in years)	-.057	***	-.046	**	-.085	***	-.026	*
Income below average (1=below)	-.028		-.031		-.033		-.014	
Education (1=higher education)	-.009		-.012		-.024		.011	
Step 3								
Live near (<50 km) of facilities for mining/ coal energy? (1=yes)	.023		-.002		.012		.054	**
Current heating with coal (1=yes)	-.042	**	-.015		-.066	***	-.035	
Preference regarding energy from coal	-.113	***	-.144	***	-.112	***	-.054	***
Evaluation of consequences of phase-out	.327	***	.290	***	.308	***	.303	
Step 4								
Identify with conservative policies	-.055	**	-.073	***	-.060	**	-.018	
Identify with liberally oriented policies	-.019		-.005		-.047	**	.002	
Identify with socially oriented policies	.030		.038		.032		.013	
Identify with environmentally oriented policies	.098	***	.047	*	.103	***	.121	***
Identify with nationally oriented policies	.014		.019		-.003		.023	
Step 5								
Campaign likely successful	.195	***	.164	***	.212	***	.161	***
Arguments are credible	.251	***	.276	***	.212	***	.203	***
Step 1 R / ΔR ²	.058 / .003		.056 / .003		.058 / .003		.058 / .003	
Step 2 R / ΔR ²	.074 / .002		.079 / .003		.072 / .002		.081 / .003	
Step 3 R / ΔR ²	.753*** / .561***		.726*** / .521***		.715*** / .506***		.641*** / .404***	
Step 4 R / ΔR ²	.763*** / .016***		.733*** / .010***		.726*** / .016***		.656*** / .020***	
Step 5 R / ΔR ²	.813*** / .077***		.782*** / .075***		.773*** / .071***		.695*** / .052***	

Note. T1=Innovation, T2=Health and Environment, T3=National interest; Responses were given on 5-point-Likert-scales with higher values signifying support / positive evaluations. For the regression analyses Likert-scaled items were Z-standardized. Significance levels: * - p<0.10, ** - p<0.05, *** - p<0.01. The table shows the standardized regression coefficients from the final model. The other variables were coded dichotomously.

6.5 Conclusions

For the experiment in Poland on campaigns against specific energy pathways a different approach from working with a DCE was chosen as the DCE method was not seen as suitable after a thorough discussion in the consortium. Instead, an information treatment was prepared to

check whether different lines of argument for an earlier coal phase-out lead to different reactions. The information was framed as a fictitious campaign for an earlier coal phase-out. In addition to the experimental design, specific questions revealed attitudes and experiences in relation to coal.

Overall, we find a positive emotional response to the information presented in the experiment as well as that credibility and success were evaluated positively while behavioural intentions were low. However, a simple direct influence of the experimental conditions could not be corroborated with the exception of small tendencies in relation to the emotional response. With regard to an earlier coal phase-out, we find that a majority of the participants is not in favour of such a strategy. Nevertheless, on average, participants expect positive rather than negative outcomes (see Table 17).

In a final step, we explored if differences between the treatments become visible if it is controlled for a variety of factors. We find a significant effect in the condition of the environmental and health treatment in such a way that this treatment is more likely to be followed by a positive emotional response. The main predictors refer to the more specific opinion around the coal industry as well as political ideology while socio-demographic variables appear to be of negligible relevance.

7 OUTLOOK

The large-sample survey results presented in this report provide valuable insights into the acceptability of certain types of SIE by the general population of a country.

First, the findings from the discrete choice experiments on investment projects in decentralized renewable electricity generation in France, Germany, and Poland highlight the importance of financial attributes such as the rate of return, the risk associated with such investments, and low minimum investment requirements. They also point to a new role by municipalities: by matching the investments by citizens, municipalities may amplify participation by citizens in such projects. Engagement in such projects is expected to be higher if profits are used to finance environmental protection rather than to support low-income households. When designing such SIE, differences in preferences across countries should be recognized. For example, citizens in Poland appear more worried about the financial risks than citizens in France and Germany.

Second, results from analysing the discrete choice experiment in France on participation in renewable energy communities suggest that the rate of return would have to be substantially higher for citizens to accept firms participating in such communities and to accept decision-making being based on capital contribution rather than on the one-member-one-vote rule. Finally, high shares of self-consumption appear crucial for the acceptability of this SIE pointing also to the role of non-monetary attributes.

Third, the findings from the discrete choice experiment in Germany on gamification through mobile apps imply that people are generally reluctant to accept such an SIE. Similarly, high subscription fees deter acceptability unless a share of the subscription fees is donated to fund nature conservation measures or to support low-income households. Adding features which nudge participants (via social comparison) and allow for gamification (via competitions) as well as expert advice are likely to spur citizen engagement with such an SIE and to support the energy transition via behavioural change.

Finally, with regard to the SIE on campaigns against certain energy pathways in Poland, we find that these campaigns tend to be perceived positively as indicated by the emotional response. Intentions to act, however, are less pronounced. The emotional response is more positive if the idea of an earlier coal exit aligns with prior experience and political ideology. Campaign arguments stressing the effects of an energy pathway on health and the environment appear more convincing than arguments stressing the effects on innovation and security of supply.

Ultimately, results from deliverable D5.3 will feed into deliverable D5.4 which assesses the future potential of SIE in EU countries.

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Appendix 1: EC summary requirements

Changes with respect to the DoA

N/A

Dissemination and uptake

Results from D5.3, together with findings from D5.2, will also feed into deliverable D5.4, which assesses the future potential of SIE in Europe.

Key findings of D5.3 will be presented at the Energy Talks Disentis in January 2022.

Deliverable D5.3. will be the basis of three to four academic papers to be presented at academic conferences and eventually submitted to international peer-reviewed academic journals.

Deliverable D5.3, the full survey, and the data sets (that do not contain any identifying information) will be made publicly available on the SONNET website and / or Zenodo.

Short Summary of results (<250 words)

This deliverable presents the statistical-econometric results of the experiments carried out in the SONNET citizen survey involving about 6,000 participants. These experiments comprise of (i) a stated preferences discrete choice experiment (DCE) in France, Germany, and Poland on investment projects in decentralised renewable electricity generation; (ii) a DCE which in France on participation in renewable energy cooperatives (REC)s; (iii) a DCE in Germany on energy gamification through mobile applications; and (iv) an experiment in Poland on campaigns against specific energy pathways.

The results from experiment (i) highlight the importance of financial attributes such (e.g. rate of return, risk) and low minimum investment requirements. Further, by matching the investments by citizens, municipalities may amplify citizen participation in such projects. Engagement is also expected to be higher if profits are used to finance environmental protection rather than to support low-income households. As for experiment (ii) in France it turns out that citizens prefer RECs without the involvement of private companies, a one-member-one-vote rule and that allow for high shares of self-consumption. In experiment (iii) on gamification through mobile apps in Germany, we find generally low interest in such an SIE, especially when subscription fees are high, even though different app features are valued by participants. Regarding experiment (iv) in Poland, we find that campaigns tend to be perceived positively as indicated by the emotional response. Intentions to act, however, are less pronounced. Campaign arguments stressing the effects of an energy pathway on health and the environmental appear more convincing than other arguments.

Evidence of accomplishment

This Deliverable and associated documents